

Numerical simulation of ship-ice interaction in brash ice channel, comparison of injection methods using CFD-DEM

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Abstract. This study explores the behavior of brash ice channels, with a particular focus on the interactions between ice particles and their collective effects on the ship hull. Emphasis is placed on both hydrodynamic forces and particle-induced loads acting on the vessel. A coupled Computational Fluid Dynamics–Discrete Element Method (CFD–DEM) framework is employed to simulate these interactions. Two distinct ice particle injection methods (Random injection and Part injection) are implemented to evaluate their influence on computational performance, particle distribution, and overall simulation fidelity. The goal is to assess how accurately these methods capture real-world ice–ship interaction phenomena. Our findings reveal that the random injector achieves a more natural particle distribution, maintaining consistent channel porosity and effectively modeling brash ice conditions. This method was computationally advantageous, reducing CPU time by approximately 80% compared to the part injector, which exhibited higher computational costs and premature bow wave effects due to its structured injection pattern. These results underscore the importance of injection methods in accurately modeling ice resistance while balancing computational demands. The insights gained from this research contribute to improving the numerical simulation of ships brash ice channels.

Key words: Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), Discrete Element Method (DEM), Brash Ice Channel, Hydrodynamics, Ship-Ice interaction

1. Introduction

Maritime operations in ice-covered regions such as the Baltic Sea, where seasonal sea ice formation occurs annually, underscore the need for detailed investigations into ship–ice interactions. Under these conditions, icebreakers create channels through level ice, enabling ice-strengthened merchant vessels to operate with reduced installed power, as they no longer need to independently break the ice themselves. However, the resulting brash ice increases resistance with respect to open water resistance and disrupts propulsion by altering hull-ice interactions and propeller performance. Predicting power requirements in brash ice is challenging due to ice dynamics and complex interactions. Accurate modeling is essential for evaluating vessel performance and determining the required installed power to optimize fuel efficiency and reduce emissions.

Research on ship-ice interaction and the added resistance of ice over open water dates back to 1889. It is believed that total resistance could be determined by summing open water resistance and the contact forces exerted by ice on the ship’s hull. The basic formulation of this resistance is presented in Eq. 1.

$$R_{tot} = R_{ice} + R_{ow} \quad (1)$$

Where R_{tot} , R_{ice} , and R_{ow} are channel resistance, ice resistance, and open water resistance, respectively. One of the most notable studies in this field was conducted by Riska et al. [1] that based on several earlier works. They explained that channel resistance is influenced by factors such as ship geometry, vessel speed, and ice thickness, which together allow for an estimation of a vessel’s resistance when operating within an ice channel. Although this method does not fully account for all contributing factors, it provides a reasonable approximation of resistance. However, through numerical modeling, the aim is to improve the prediction and estimation of forces to enable more reliable vessel designs.

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In recent years, model-scale tests have been conducted on ships navigating brash ice channels, analyzing the vessel's resistance. Ice resistance is determined by comparing the force required to move a ship through a channel with and without ice. Similarly, previous research [[10], [13], [11], [7]] have attempted to extract the contact forces between the ice and the hull, combining them with the open-water resistance to estimate the overall channel resistance. In addition to model-scale experiments, numerical simulations have been conducted to gain deeper insights into the ship-ice interaction phenomena. Throughout these studies, various numerical parameters were analyzed. Key properties—such as the restitution coefficient, friction coefficient, and particle shape—were found to significantly affect ice behavior and, consequently, the accuracy of ship-ice interaction models. To provide a clearer understanding, the effects of these numerical properties are explained below.

The restitution coefficient governs the elasticity of particle collisions, affecting energy dissipation during impacts and directly influencing ship-ice interaction and resistance calculations. StarCCM+ software suggests a default value of 0.5, although various studies have tested values ranging from 0.1 to 0.81. Zhang et al. [10] used 0.5, with other values showing minimal impact on results. Koivurova [12] found that a higher restitution coefficient led to more uniform velocity and less ice accumulation at the bow, while a lower value led to faster channel closure and increased ice piling at the bow.

The friction coefficient influences the interaction between particles, affecting energy dissipation, ice accumulation, and overall ship resistance. Two types of friction coefficients are of particular importance: ice-ice friction and ice-ship friction. Ice-ice friction coefficients typically range from 0.05 to 1, with lower values resulting in more realistic ice particle interactions and better resistance predictions [4]. Higher friction led to thicker ice layers and earlier channel closure, as reported by Koivurova [12] and Seo et al. [13]. Ship-ice friction values typically range from 0.05 to 0.1. Koivurova [12] demonstrated that higher ship-ice friction resulted in thicker ice accumulation and faster channel closure, while Seo et al. [13] used 0.05 to ensure accurate results without overestimating ice force.

Particle shape plays a crucial role in friction and resistance. Irregular or angular particles have more contact points, increasing friction and energy dissipation. Luo et al. [2] tested tetrahedral and irregular polyhedral shapes, with tetrahedral particles providing more accurate resistance predictions. Koivurova [12] found that cylindrical particles required more computational time but exhibited different channel closing patterns compared to spherical particles.

Factors such as stiffness and Young's modulus also influence particle behavior. Xie et al. [11] found that an ice stiffness of 1000 N/m provided the most accurate results, while Voutilainen [7] showed that Young's modulus had minimal impact on ice trajectories when reduced. Domain properties, including ice concentration, channel width, and injector properties, are critical in simulating ship-ice interactions. Higher ice concentration leads to more frequent interactions between the ship and ice, increasing resistance and energy consumption. Xie et al. [11] and Zou et al. [6] observed that ice resistance and force rise significantly with concentrations exceeding 60%, resulting in faster ice accumulation and displacement. Channel width influences ice distribution around the ship, with narrower channels amplifying wave heights and increasing ship resistance. Xie et al. [11] found that while wider channels reduce resistance, this effect becomes negligible once the distance to the channel walls exceeds approximately eight times the ship's breadth, at which point the environment can no longer be considered a channel.

Three common contact models used in ship-ice simulations are Walton Braun (WB), Hertz Mindlin (HM), and Linear Spring (LS). The Hertz Mindlin model provides better accuracy, as reported by Luo et al. [2], but the Linear Spring model is often preferred for its simplicity and computational efficiency [8]. CFD-DEM coupling can be one-way or two-way. One-way coupling, where the fluid influences the particles but not vice versa, is computationally efficient and commonly used in low-speed simulations [6]. Two-way coupling, where both the fluid and particles interact, is necessary for more complex simulations, such as high-speed ships [2].

These studies have illuminated the complexity of ship-ice interactions. However, a significant challenge remains in developing reliable numerical methods to accurately represent brash ice formation, distribution, and the dynamics of ship-ice contact, particularly concerning resistance and impact forces. A key observation, based on previous research, is that injector characteristics, specifically how they influence the introduction of numerical channels have often been overlooked. This study aims to enhance numerical modeling techniques for brash ice interactions by focusing on the precise introduction of ice particles into

the computational domain. To achieve this, we explore various methods for injecting ice particles into simulations and assess their efficiency and accuracy.

2. Numerical Method

2.1. Computational Fluid Dynamics

The study of fluid flow around a ship hull, the complexity stems from solving the nonlinear partial differential Navier-Stokes equations, where the continuity and momentum equations are as follows:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot [\mu (\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T)] + \rho\mathbf{g}. \quad (3)$$

Eq. 2 and Eq. 3 represents the conservation of mass and momentum, respectively. Here, \mathbf{u} is the velocity component, and in Eq. 3 the left-hand side represents the material derivative of velocity \mathbf{u} , with ρ being the fluid density, and capturing the acceleration (the convective term). The right-hand side includes the pressure gradient p , viscous diffusion characterized by the dynamic viscosity μ , and body forces such as gravity represented by \mathbf{g} .

2.1.1. Turbulence Model

This research employs Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) to balance numerical accuracy and efficiency, with computational demand primarily driven by boundary layer resolution. However, the majority of comparable studies, [7], [11], [5], [10], and [2] also recommend this approach. By employing this method, it is possible to capture the mean flow behavior while accounting for fluctuating turbulent effects. By averaging the continuity (Eq. 2) and momentum (Eq. 3) equations based on the RANS method, they can be written as:

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{u}} = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\bar{\mathbf{u}})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\bar{\mathbf{u}} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{u}}) = -\nabla \bar{p} + \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma} + \mathbf{R}) + \rho\mathbf{g}. \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{R} = -\overline{\rho\mathbf{u}' \otimes \mathbf{u}'} \quad (6)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \rho\nu (\nabla\bar{\mathbf{u}} + (\nabla\bar{\mathbf{u}})^T) \quad (7)$$

Eq. 4, states that while the continuity equation remains the same, the mean velocities are used instead of the instantaneous velocities. σ is the viscous stress, and \mathbf{R} is the Reynolds stress that has multiple methods to be modeled. Among the possible modeling options, $K - \omega$ SST (Shear Stress Transport) turbulence model was used. By utilizing turbulent kinetic energy (k) and the specific dissipation rate (ω). The model blends the $k - \epsilon$ model in free-stream regions with the near-wall accuracy of the $k - \omega$ model, providing improved predictions across boundary layers and separation zones.

2.2. Discrete Element Method

Brash ice, which represents the discrete phase within the simulation domain, is modeled as part of the Lagrangian phase. The Discrete Element Method (DEM) is used to study these particles. This method iteratively solves for the location and velocity while taking forces into account for each iteration and updates the position of the elements within the domain. The solver operates on a small time-step loop. The motion of an individual DEM particle follows Newton's second law:

$$m_p \frac{d\mathbf{U}_p}{dt} = \mathbf{F}_g + \mathbf{F}_{SL} + \mathbf{F}_d + \mathbf{F}_p + \mathbf{F}_{vm} + \mathbf{F}_c \quad (8)$$

Where m_p is the mass, \mathbf{U}_p is the translational velocity, and the right-hand side of the equation consists of gravitational force \mathbf{F}_g , shear lift force \mathbf{F}_{SL} , drag force \mathbf{F}_d , pressure force \mathbf{F}_p , virtual mass force \mathbf{F}_{vm} ,

Figure 1: Illustration of contact forces on the impact of two particles [17].

and contact force \mathbf{F}_c [17]. Apart from the calculation of forces, the rotational momentum of the particles must be taken into account:

$$\mathbf{I}_p \frac{d\boldsymbol{\omega}_p}{dt} = \mathbf{M}_d + \mathbf{M}_c \quad (9)$$

\mathbf{I}_p is a second-order tensor of moment of inertia, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_p$ is the angular velocity, \mathbf{M}_d indicates the drag moment brought on by rotational drag, and \mathbf{M}_c signifies the moment induced by the contact force.

Various approaches exist for modeling contact forces in DEM. Among them, the linear spring-dashpot model, developed by Cundall and Strack [18] was chosen for its simplicity and efficiency. It represents normal force with a linear spring-dashpot and tangential force with a series spring-dashpot-slider. The model assumes linear springs with constant stiffness, simplifying interactions. Equations 10 and 11 define the forces and it is shown in Figure 1.

The normal force F_n is defined as:

$$F_n = -K_n d_n - N_n v_n \quad (10)$$

Where d_n is the amount of overlap, K_n is the normal spring stiffness coefficient, N_n is the normal damping, and v_n is the normal velocity components of the relative sphere surface velocity at the contact point.

The tangential contact force F_t is divided into dynamic and static friction forces. When the tangential contact force exceeds the static friction force, it is modeled as Coulomb friction. The tangential force is defined as:

$$F_t = \begin{cases} -K_t d_t - N_t v_t & \text{if } |K_t d_t| \geq |K_n d_n| C_{fs} \\ \frac{|K_n d_n| C_{fs} d_t}{|d_t|} & \text{if } |K_t d_t| < |K_n d_n| C_{fs} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Where d_t is the amount of particle overlap inside on another, C_{fs} is the static friction coefficient, K_t is the tangential spring stiffness, N_t is the tangential damping, and v_t is the tangential velocity components of the relative sphere surface velocity at the contact point.

2.3. Multiphase modelling

The CFD-DEM algorithm shares computational cells among air, water (Eulerian phases), and ice particles (Lagrangian phase). Ice reduces the fluid volume in each cell, affecting force and velocity calculations. The computational cell's volume is partitioned among air, water, and ice to ensure accurate phase interactions. Equations define total cell volume, fluid volume fraction, and phase-specific volume fractions. These considerations influence the solver equations discussed in the next section. A schematic illustrates how volume is divided within a computational cell to represent interactions accurately.

$$V = \sum_i V_i^F + \sum_i V_i^S + \sum_i V_i^L \quad (12)$$

The volume fraction for one phase of the fluid α_i is defined as the ratio of volume occupied by that phase to the total fluid volume:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i = 1, \quad \alpha_i = \frac{V_i^F}{\sum_i V_i^F} \quad (13)$$

Phases within a cell are identified by the volume fraction α_i , where N is the total number of phases. Phase i is absent from the cell if $\alpha_i = 0$; phase i is fully occupied if $\alpha_i = 1$. Values between 0 and 1 indicate an interface between phases. When more than one fluid is present, it is regarded as a mixture.

$$\rho = \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i \alpha_i, \quad \mu = \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i \alpha_i \quad (14)$$

Where, ρ_i is the density, μ_i is the dynamic viscosity of phase i [17]. For the two phases, the VOF transport equation is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \alpha_i) = 0 \quad (15)$$

2.4. Solution Algorithm

The solution algorithm integrates the CFD solver which iteratively solves the Navier-Stokes equations, updating pressure and velocity fields until convergence. The DEM framework tracks discrete particle motion, detecting contacts, computing forces, and updating velocities. The DEM operates with sub-time steps for accuracy and stability, feeding updated particle data back into the CFD solver. The algorithm uses five coupling iterations per time step. Two-way coupling ensures reciprocal interactions between fluid and particles, modifying fluid behavior based on the solid phase's volume fraction. This algorithm is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Flowchart of the CFD-DEM Coupled Solution Algorithm Utilizing the SIMPLE Method.

2.4.1. Momentum Exchange

Substepping facilitates momentum exchange between particles and fluid, where particle momentum acts as a source term in CFD cells. According to Newton’s third law, momentum transfer from particles to fluid must equal the reverse. The momentum source term for unsteady simulations is given by:

$$\mathbf{S}_v = -\frac{1}{\Delta t} \sum_{\pi} \left(\int_t^{t+\Delta t} \int_{V_c} \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_{\pi}) \mathbf{n}_{\pi} (\mathbf{F}_{\text{SL}} + \mathbf{F}_d + \mathbf{F}_p + \mathbf{F}_{\text{vm}} + \dot{m} \times \mathbf{v}_p) dV dt \right) \quad (16)$$

where π indicates a particle parcel, δ is the Dirac delta function, \mathbf{v}_p is the particle’s velocity, and \dot{m} is the mass transfer rate to the particle. The fluid momentum equation incorporates the resulting source term \mathbf{S}_v .

2.4.2. Cell Clustering

In optimal cases, DEM particles fit within CFD computational cells, but for brash ice, particles are larger than CFD cells. To enhance accuracy, a two-grid strategy is applied, where adjacent cells form larger virtual cells to compute fluid-particle interactions. These interactions are then redistributed to individual cells. To ensure simulation stability, the Smooth Large Particle and Volume Source Smoothing methods are used with a smoothing parameter of 0.15 m, approximately three times the particle diameter. Volume Source Smoothing distributes the Lagrangian phase impact across multiple cells, while Smooth Large Particle improves large particle representation within the Eulerian mesh, enabling precise two-way coupling between fluid and solid phases [17].

3. Test Setup

3.1. Model Scale Test

The model-scale tests conducted by [7] were performed in the Aker Arctic ice basin, using a simplified vessel geometry, the characteristics of which are summarized in Table 1. The experiment began with determining the open-water resistance of the vessel in an ice-free channel. Subsequently, ice pieces shown in Figure 4 were added into the channel to evaluate the additional forces exerted by the ice on the ship’s hull. The difference between the total resistance measured in the ice-filled channel and that in the ice-free condition represents the force induced by the ice particles on the hull. Subsequently, after knowing the experimental results, the numerical solution assists us in predicting the reality with more accurate measures described in the following section. In reality, ice particles remain stationary until the ship comes into contact with them. However, in simulations, brash ice fields need to be actively introduced into the computational domain.

3.2. Geometry And Boundary Conditions

The domain has a total length of $7L$, with the inlet placed $1.5L$ from the bow and the outflow $4.5L$ from the stern. The domain’s height is $0.5L$, and the basin depth is $0.35L$, as detailed in Table 1. The solid ice along the channel’s sides is positioned based on the ice and water densities, with 0.3 cm above and 2.7 cm below the free surface. The boundary conditions, shown in Figure 3, are based on the model test setup. A pressure outlet is placed on the right side, with velocity inlets at the top and left. No-slip walls are applied to the ship’s geometry, ice edges, and the domain’s sides and bottom. The solid ice, along with the left and right walls, moves with the same velocity as the inlet, creating a stationary reference frame for the ship. The solid-level ice is modeled with the same DEM parameters as brash ice. Trials are conducted at a 1:20 scale with a matching Froude number of 0.105 and a damping length of 5 meters at the inlet and outlet, based on experimental tests from [7]. The ice particles, shown in Figure 4, are modeled using spheres. Cylindrical ice pieces (4 cm diameter, 3 cm height) are formed with 14 spheres. These dimensions ensure a 64 mm brash ice channel thickness while optimizing computational efficiency by matching experimental particle volume.

Table 1: Model-Scale Experiment Details.

Parameter	Value
Ice Basin Dimensions	75 m (length) 8 m (width) 2.1 m (depth)
Water Density	1011 kg/m ³
Dynamic Viscosity	0.00183 Pa·s
Vessel Geometry	Cuboid
Vessel Dimensions	6 m (length, L) 1 m (beam, B) 1 m (depth, d) 0.6 m (draft, D)
Half-Cylinder Diameter	1 m (equal to B)

Figure 3: Illustration of the simulation geometry.

(a) Model Scale Ice [7]

(b) Numerical ice

Figure 4: Demonstration ice particles made in StarCCM+ software. (a) Model scale ice [7] (b) Cylindrical ice (Numerical)

Figure 5: Demonstration mesh made in StarCCM+ (a) Top view, (b) Side view, (c) Front view.

Table 2: Grid independency study results.

Grid	Cell Count (M)	Cell Size (m)	R_{ow} [N]
Grid 1	3.02	0.21	80.25
Grid 2	1.53	0.28	80.90
Grid 3	0.86	0.35	81.48
Grid 4	0.60	0.42	82.69

3.3. Mesh

The mesh was generated using a trimmed mesher with prism layers to ensure accurate boundary layer resolution near wetted surfaces. Key parameters include prismatic layer thickness, number of layers, and growth rates. The meshing procedure for the model-scale ship utilized a trimmed mesher with hexahedral cells, a base size of 0.28 m, a target surface size of 72%, a minimum surface size of 2%, six prismatic layers with a thickness of 8% of the base size, a medium volume growth rate, and an expansion ratio of 1.1 for the prism layer.

3.4. Verification and validation

The open water simulation at 7 knots, conducted without ice, is used to assess mesh sensitivity and verify the accuracy of the numerical method. Four mesh resolutions are tested, with finer grids providing more accurate flow representation. As shown in Table 2 and Figure 6, resistance values converge with mesh refinement, approaching the experimental result of 79.25 N reported by Voutilainen [7]. The mean resistance is calculated from the last 10 seconds of simulation, though some deviation from experiments is expected due to modeling and measurement uncertainties.

Building on previous findings, mesh resolution significantly influences the accuracy of wave profile representation in open water simulations. As shown in Figure 7, finer meshes produce more detailed wave shapes and better capture the complex interactions between the ship and surrounding water, including the bow wave and wake.

Figure 6: Effect of mesh resolution on calculated resistance values.

Figure 7: Demonstration wave propagation in different cell sizes for open water simulation.

Higher-resolution meshes capture finer details and sharp changes in the wave surface, leading to a more accurate representation of wave height, wavelength, and propagation speed, as shown in Figure 7. Lower-resolution meshes, on the other hand, smooth out these characteristics, possibly losing important details and warping the wave profile, which leads to an imprecise visualization of the fluid domain. Ultimately, the wave profile directly impacts the pressure distribution throughout the hull. Realistic pressure fluctuations are ensured via precise waveforms, which are captured by fine meshes as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 9: Illustration of the injector position in respect of the ship in the channel.

Figure 8: Demonstration wave propagation in the model scale and the selected mesh (grid 2).

Eventually, balancing computational accuracy with computational cost is required. Although Grid 1 achieved the best accuracy, it is highly computationally expensive. Therefore, Grid 2 is chosen as the base of the simulation.

3.5. Injector

The key aspect of this study is the use of injectors, computational tools designed to introduce ice particles into the simulation domain, ensuring accurate representation of ice channels and interactions with the ship's hull. The injectors are illustrated in Figure 9. The Random injector is simply a box with a length of L , and other characteristics mentioned below that produce a non-uniform particle distribution resembling real brash ice, allowing flexible injection locations and density control. Ice pieces are injected simultaneously, with periodic repetition to maintain porosity. The Part injector is a surface capable of injecting particles at a specific rate of $6.18 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, as determined using Eq. 18. In contrast, this method enables a semi-uniform particle injection by defining a volumetric flow rate across a surface, allowing for controlled particle distribution within the domain.

Both injectors are positioned $0.5L$ away from the ship's bow, with a width of $2B$, and a height sufficient to accommodate two layers of ice stacked on top of each other 64 mm as shown in Figure 9. The target porosity of the channel is 60%, and the volume of ice pieces are $3.7654 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3$. The ITTC [15] formula

determines particle count.

$$\text{Porosity} = 1 - \frac{N_{ice} V_{ice}}{V_{total}} \quad (17)$$

Where N_{ice} represents the number of particles within the specified volume, V_{ice} denotes the volume of each ice particle, V_{total} refers to the total volume under consideration, within which the porosity is being determined. Similarly, the injection rate of the Part injector through the surface is calculated based on the particle velocity and the surface geometry as follows:

$$Q = H_{av} \cdot 2B \cdot u_g \cdot \text{porosity} \quad (18)$$

where Q represents the volume flow rate, H_{av} is the average brash ice thickness, B denotes the beam width of the geometry, u_g is the velocity of the geometry, and desired porosity is the targeted porosity level.

4. Results

To assess how the injection method influences the simulation results, a CFD-DEM model is used with specific ice properties: Young's modulus of 90 MPa, density of 920 kg/m³, and channel porosity of 60%. The friction coefficients are set to 0.54 for ice-ice contact and 0.10 for ice-geometry contact. Both ice-ice and ice-geometry restitution coefficients are 0.81, and the Poisson's ratio is 0.3.

4.1. Formation of Channel

In the Part injector method, particles are introduced sequentially in rows from the surface until they fully surround the ship. In contrast, the Random injection method releases all ice particles at once within a predefined box, after which they begin moving with the ship's velocity. To maintain a consistent channel porosity of 60%, the injection cycle repeats once the last particle exits the box. While the overall visual distribution of particles remains consistent, once the channel is fully covered, a more detailed investigation is required to uncover subtle differences in particle interactions and behavior that may influence the simulation results. For visualization purposes, a time interval of 3 seconds was used to demonstrate the process as illustrated in Figure 10.

4.2. Porosity Of The Channel

The only difference between the simulation results is how the ice pieces are introduced into the simulation domain, while all simulation parameters remain unchanged to assess whether the physics of the problem is affected. The considered volume has a length of $0.5L$, a width of $2B$, and a height that accommodates up to three layers of ice particles. The height is approximately 0.12 m at the bow and aft sections, while the side sections, where particle accumulation is higher, have a box height of up to 0.2 m. Considering the volume of each ice piece and the total suggested volume, the setup should approximately contain 7,650 ice particles within the box. To assess porosity at different locations near the ship, four specific points along the ship's length are considered: at $-0.5L$ (0.5L before the particles encounter the ship), at $0.0L$ (the bow), at $0.5L$ (midship), at $1.0L$ (the stern), and at $1.5L$ (0.5L behind the ship). These cross-sections enable a detailed analysis of porosity around the ship and are illustrated in Figure 11. The number of particles in each section is calculated using the formula suggested by ITTC (Eq. 17).

Figure 11 shows that both injection methods create similar channel shapes, but the Part injector results in a denser ice buildup near the bow, suggesting stronger ice-ship interaction due to deeper particle accumulation. In contrast, the Random injector produces a more scattered distribution. Differences observed behind the ship (Figure 11 Sec.IV) may be due to numerical issues. Particle counts at different locations are provided in Table 3.

The errors in particle numbers and porosity are negligible compared to the target values. Particle accumulation is more pronounced near the bow, but overall, the injection method does not significantly impact the particle distribution across the domain. The values are maintained consistently throughout the simulation to ensure the desired porosity. Both injection methods result in similar particle distributions.

Figure 10: Visualization of brush ice formation using both Part and Random injection method at 3-second intervals for a ship moving at a velocity of 7 knots.

Table 3: Number of particles and the porosity in each injection method in various locations.

Location of the Section	Part injector		Random injector	
	Number of Particles	Porosity (%)	Number of Particles	Porosity (%)
Sec.[I] 0.5 L away from bow	7818	59.14	7611	60.19
Sec.[II] at the bow	7351	61.56	7590	60.30
Sec.[III] midship	7495	60.80	7680	59.83
Sec.[IV] 0.5 L away from stern	7682	59.82	7662	59.92

Figure 11: Visualization of the formed brush ice channel from different perspectives and particle position using (a) Part injector, (b) Random injector.

Table 4: A comparison of model-scale results and simulation findings from this study and experimental one [7], focusing on the total resistance of the channel.

Cases	Resistance (N)
Voutilainen Experimental [7]	87.96
Present work (Part injector)	90.52
Present work (Random injector)	88.77

4.3. Observation of Ship-Ice Interaction

4.3.1. Contact Force

Voutilainen [7] reported that ice contact forces on the ship increased resistance by approximately 10 N. This value is added to the open-water resistance, and the total channel resistance is presented in Table 4. The average contact force between the ice and the ship for both injection methods is computed and shown in Figure 12. The ice contact force applied to the ship's hull is added to the open-water resistance, which was previously computed and presented in Figure 6 and Table 2 for Grid 2. Moreover, to determine the total resistance encountered by the ship in the brush ice channel, Eq. 1 is used.

Figure 12 shows that contact forces on the ship vary depending on the injection method. The Part injector method, with a structured particle distribution, leads to synchronized impacts, resulting in periodic force oscillations and stronger ice-ship interactions near the bow. In contrast, the Random injector method, with a more dispersed particle distribution, results in fewer simultaneous impacts, lower average forces, and reduced peak magnitudes, despite similar porosity levels in both methods.

Although the overall sum of contact forces doesn't show significant differences, the frequency of these forces provides useful insights into particle-ship interactions. Figure 13 illustrates contact occurrences and

Figure 12: Sum of contact force experienced by the ship with the velocity of 7 kn in brush ice channel using (a) Part injector, (b) Random injector.

Figure 13: Instantaneous contact DEM force experienced by the ship with the velocity of 7 kn in brash ice channel using (a) Part injector, (b) Random injector.

Figure 14: Illustration of pressure and shear resistance oscillation after introducing DEM particles with the velocity of 7 kn in brash ice channel using (a) Part injector [Injection time at $T=81$ s], (b) Random injector [Injection time at $T=84$ s]

corresponding force magnitudes for both methods. Despite the ship being surrounded by brash ice, only a few contact points occur at any given time. Despite the denser particle accumulation and larger contact forces observed with the Part injector method, as shown in Figure 11 and Table 4, it was expected to see more contact with the ship. However, the Random injector method results in more consistent contact. This doesn't mean that contact patterns are uniform across all time steps. To better assess the impact frequency of both methods in real-world conditions, further targeted experiments are needed.

4.3.2. Effect of Ice on Open Water Resistance

The previous findings highlight the mechanisms behind ship-ice interactions. When DEM particles are introduced, noticeable oscillations in pressure and shear resistance occur, disturbing the surrounding fluid. These oscillations intensify as particles approach the ship, as shown in Figure 14. Particles are injected simultaneously, causing a sharp increase in water level and generating a pressure wave toward the ship. In simulations, pressure is assumed to propagate instantly, so changes in the pressure field are immediate, even with a few particle impacts. The Random injector method, introducing more particles, results in a higher peak in open water resistance (Figure 14), suggesting that pressure waves, even with fewer direct impacts, still exert force on the ship's hull.

When the injector type is changed, the instantaneous hydrodynamic resistance varies significantly, accompanied by notable fluctuations in the immediate pressure and shear forces, which contribute to the open-water resistance. However, as shown in Figure 14, the average hydrodynamic resistance increases only slightly.

The observed discrepancy of the open water resistance between the two injection methods can be explained by several factors, with local versus global effects playing a key role. Localized, transient interactions between particles and the ship's surface cause spikes in pressure and shear, driven by high-contact forces during collisions. However, these fluctuations have minimal impact on overall resistance as they av-

Figure 15: Comparison of CPU time in injector properties between the random and Part injector methods.

erage out over time. The surrounding fluid’s damping effect helps reduce larger fluctuations in pressure and shear, mitigating their impact on total hydrodynamic resistance. Complex interactions between the fluid and particles may create localized disturbances, but the relationship between particle addition and resistance is not linear. The fluctuating forces are likely due to the boundary layer interaction between particles and the hull, which alters shear stress and pressure distribution. In StarCCM+ [17], particles are treated as voids, reducing the fluid volume and potentially causing numerical noise. Despite these disturbances, the total resistance increase is modest (around 1 N), indicating a minimal global impact.

4.4. CPU Time

The investigation of particle injection methods shows minimal impact on the final results, with slight differences in contact force and the number of contacts. A key factor is the trade-off between accuracy and computational cost. The Part injector method significantly increases computational cost, as the DEM solver is activated when the first row of particles is injected. Within 3 seconds, the computational demand nearly doubles, and by the time the ship is fully covered in ice, the cost has increased by a factor of 10. This increase is due to the two-way coupling method, where DEM equations are solved for each particle, and forces are transferred to the fluid phase, along with the continuous introduction and tracking of new particles. Both injectors yield similar results, but the Part injector demands more computational resources due to its introduction of particles in bulk, creating high-density regions and increasing interaction complexity. This requires frequent checks for particle overlap, adding significant overhead. On the other hand, the Random injector produces comparable outcomes at only one-fifth of the computational cost, as it distributes particles more evenly, reducing clustering and overlap. It also checks for overlap only once at injection, greatly reducing the solver’s workload. As shown in Figure 15, particles are assigned to cells upon injection and activated to solve the DEM equations. The most computationally intensive stage is contact detection, where the solver evaluates particle overlaps to identify interactions, which accounts for around 80% of the computational cost. After contact resolution, the particle motion dynamically adjusts the activation order of cells as particles are added or removed during the simulation.

5. Conclusion

The comparison of the obtained resistance results shows that the Random injector method provides a more computationally efficient solution, reducing CPU time by approximately 80% compared to the Part injector method; however, this is only in comparison regarding resistance, and more experimental experiments are required. Despite this efficiency, the Random injector maintains similar total channel resistance, particle distributions, and channel porosity values. Minor differences in particle accumulation near the bow were observed, but the Random injector records more contacts, which requires further experimental obser-

vation data. While the introduction of DEM particles causes transient pressure and shear fluctuations, their overall impact on open-water resistance remains minimal. Therefore, the Random injector method is the optimal choice for full-scale numerical simulations, offering both efficiency and accuracy, while emphasizing the importance of selecting the appropriate injection method.

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